

CO-ORDINATED COPPER COMPOUNDS WITH PROPYLENEDIAMINE.

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Literature shows that complex propylenediamine salts of copper were unknown. In our attempts to prepare *tris*-propylenediamine salts with a view to their resolution into optical isomers we have discovered *bis*-propylenediamine salts which were not resolvable. These salts are violet in colour, very soluble in water yielding beautiful violet coloured solutions. The *d*-tartrate, *d*-camphor sulphate and nitronate have been prepared and their rotations measured.

Literature shows that copper forms complex ethylenediamine salts, but complex propylenediamine salts of copper were hitherto unknown. *bis*-Propylenediamine salts were however obtained by adding two molecular proportions of propylenediamine to aqueous solutions of soluble copper salts. All the solid salts are stable in air and possess beautiful violet colour, sulphate being bluish violet. They are extremely soluble in water and yield violet coloured solutions of different shades. The salts are not acted upon by dilute caustic alkalis, but acids, and even dilute acetic acid, decompose them as in the case of complex ammonia and ethylenediamine salts and their violet colour is destroyed showing the decomposition of the coordination group. The specific rotations of the *d*-tartrate, *d*-camphor sulphate and nitronate were measured.

EXPERIMENTAL.

bis-Propylenediamine-cupric Chlorides.—Two molecules of propylenediamine added to one molecule of cupric chloride dissolved in water gave a pink-violet solution. On evaporation in vacuum a sticky mass was obtained. This was washed with a mixture of alcohol and ether when a solid of deep violet colour was obtained. It was crystallised from water and purified by recrystallisation or in the alternative by dissolving in alcohol and precipitating by means of ether. In the latter case the solid came out paler in colour. On drying in a vacuum desiccator the products obtained in the two cases were found to be identical. The complex chloride is fairly soluble in alcohol but insoluble in ether and acetone. (Found: Cu, 22.81; N, 19.97. $[\text{Cupn}_2]\text{Cl}_2$ required Cu, 22.5; N, 19.82 per cent).

bis-Propylenediamine-cupric bromide was prepared by adding two molecular proportions of propylenediamine to aqueous solution of cupric bromide in the cold and evaporating the mixture in vacuum. The solid obtained was at once crystalline and of violet colour. It was purified by recrystallisation from water and afterwards dried in a vacuum desiccator. The complex bromide could also be precipitated from the original solution by alcohol in which solvent it is only sparingly soluble. The solid obtained in this way was pale blue in colour but gave an identical product when dried in vacuum. It is insoluble in ether and acetone. (Found: Cu, 17.45; N, 15.15. $[\text{Cupn}_2] \text{Br}_2$ requires Cu, 17.1; N, 15.07 per cent).

bis-Propylenediamine-cupric iodide was prepared according to the method of Morgan. Cuprous iodide (1 mol.) and propylenediamine (2 mols.) were shaken in water containing a small amount of iodine. An intense violet colour was developed immediately although but little cuprous iodide dissolved. The mixture was heated to 60° while air was bubbled through it. The cuprous salt then passed into solution. The filtered solution was evaporated in vacuum. The sticky mass obtained was washed with a mixture of alcohol and ether and then crystallised from water. The complex iodide could also be precipitated out with alcohol. The compound was analysed after drying in vacuum over sulphuric acid. (Found: Cu, 13.7; N, 12.1. $[\text{Cupn}_2] \text{I}_2$ requires Cu, 13.64; N, 12 per cent). The unstable cupric iodide has thus been stabilised as in the case of the corresponding ethylenediamine salt by Morgan.

bis-Propylenediamine-cupric Sulphate.—Copper sulphate (1 mol.) and propylenediamine (2 mols.) yielded a purple violet solution. Alcohol precipitated the complex sulphate as a solid of sky-blue colour. It was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and water and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The complex sulphate is insoluble in alcohol, ether and acetone. On dissolving in water, the colour of the solid changed to purple violet. (Found; Cu, 20.7; N, 18.35. $[\text{Cupn}_2] \text{SO}_4$ requires Cu, 20.7; N, 18.2 per cent).

bis-Propylenediamine-cupric Nitrate.—Two molecular proportions of propylenediamine were added to one of copper nitrate in aqueous solution. Alcohol did not precipitate the complex nitrate from the mixture. The solution was evaporated in vacuum and the solid obtained washed with alcohol. The complex nitrate appeared from its solution in water as deep

violet crystals. It is very slightly soluble in alcohol. {Found: Cu, 19.1; N, 25.1. $[\text{Cupn}_2] (\text{NO}_3)_2$ requires Cu, 18.9; N, 25 per cent}.

bis-Propylenediamine-cupric Tartrate.—The method of preparation from barium tartrate and *bis*-propylenediamine cupric sulphate was not satisfactory. The action of silver tartrate on the complex chloride was found to be equally unsatisfactory. The best method of preparing the complex tartrate was to add a slight excess of propylenediamine to copper tartrate suspended in water. The solid quickly dissolved giving a deep purple solution from which the compound could be precipitated by methyl alcohol. It was purified by crystallisation from water and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. Alternatively the solution was evaporated almost to dryness on a water bath and the solid which separated pressed upon a porous tile and further purified. (Found: Cu, 17.30; N, 15.58. $[\text{Cupn}_2] \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$ requires Cu, 17.66; N, 15.57 per cent). Specific rotation obtained with 5% solution at 32° is $+21^\circ$.

bis-Propylenediamine-cupric camphor sulphonate.—Silver salt of camphor sulphuric acid was added to a solution of *bis*-propylenediamine cupric chloride till the precipitate of silver chloride ceased to be formed. The solution separated from silver chloride was deep violet. On evaporation in vacuum, a solid mass was obtained. It was washed with alcohol and crystallised from water. The complex sulphonate appeared as deep violet crystals. It was dried in vacuum. {Found: Cu, 9.1; N, 8.25. $[\text{Cupn}_2]-(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{SO}_4)_2$ requires Cu, 9.43; N, 8.31 per cent}. Specific rotation obtained with 5% solution at 32° is $+26^\circ$.

bis-Propylenediamine-cupric Hydroxide.—*bis*-Propylenediamine-cupric chloride was dissolved in water and freshly prepared silver oxide was added to the solution. The mixture was stirred thoroughly and after a few hours filtered. The filtered solution was tested free from chloride. The violet coloured filtrate when evaporated in vacuum turned into a dark solid. It was twice crystallised from water and dried in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. {Found: Cu, 25.74; N, 22.91. $[\text{Cupn}_2] (\text{OH})_2$ requires Cu, 25.87; N, 22.8 per cent}.

bis-Propylenediamine-cupric Nitronate.—*bis*-Propylenediamine-cupric hydroxide was treated with nitrocamphor. Some nitrocamphor dissolved. A little residue left was filtered off. The solution which was of light violet

colour was evaporated in vacuum. The solid obtained was pale pink. It was dried in vacuum. Acetic acid precipitated nitrocamphor from a solution of the complex nitronate. It is insoluble in ether and alcohol. {Found: Cu, 10.14; N, 13.76. $[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})_2] (\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N})_2$ requires Cu, 10.5; N, 13.9 per cent}. Specific rotation obtained with 5% solution at 32° is $+107^\circ$.

bis-Propylenediamine-cupric acetate was obtained from copper acetate (1 mol.) and propylenediamine (2 mol.). The solid mass obtained by evaporation of the mixture of the solutions of above two substances could be obtained in the pure state after repeated crystallisations from water. The complex acetate is insoluble in ether. {Found: Cu, 19.33; N, 16.85; $[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})_2] (\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_2$ requires Cu, 19.27; N, 17 per cent}.

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